

Epidemiology of the Nutritional Status of School Aged Children (2-10 years) Affected by Malaria in Bamenda

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More Information

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Abstract

The objective of this study was therefore to assess the nutritional status of school aged children affected by malaria in Bamenda. This was conducted using a population of 397 for children whose parents consented. The data collected was analysed using SPSS version 23 and findings revealed that majority (52.4%) were females, 26.4% aged between 8-9years, 40.8% had occupations not specified, 64% were Christians, 70.8% were of the grass field, 65.2% earned less than 50.000frs per month and 49.9% had attained secondary education. For the BMI classification, majority (19.1%) and (11.5) for girls and boys respectively, were classified as moderately malnourished. Clinical data revealed that majority (81.1%) had pallor nails, 58.9% had scaly skin, 50.6% had week extremities, 40.8% had pale eyes, 40.1% had pale and dry eyes, 51.4% had temperature >37.5 while a few (24.7%) had brittle hair and mouth sore (29.7%). Majority (70.5%) consumed cereals, 12.6% ate legumes, 5.5% ate meat/fish/eggs, 4.5% ate milk/dairy, 3.8% ate vegetables and 3% ate fruits. Majority (60.7%) did not sleep under mosquito net, 58.4% accepted there is stagnant water and bushes around their house, 65.7% had monthly incomes <50.000frs, 59.2% did not eat green leafy vegetables, bananas, apples, meat, beans, chicken, 75.8% did not eat okro, meat, poultry, guavas, mushroom, pumk in seeds, pork, beans, yoghurt. The study concluded that moderate malnutrition and little consumption of vegetables, legumes, fruits, meat/fish/egg, milk/dairy products were nutritional problems on the nutritional status of school aged children affected by malaria in Bamenda.

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Introduction

School aged children are the age group most commonly infected with malaria parasites and their infections are usually asymptomatic, go unnoticed and thus never get treated, resulting in anaemia, reduced ability to concentrate and learn in school, and if sick lead to

school absenteeism. Malnourished children are therefore at high risk of illnesses and mortality. Malnutrition plays an important role in more than half of all child deaths worldwide and has adverse effects on the health status of children aged 0 to 5 years [1]. It also promotes an increased susceptibility to infection,

affects school performance and cognitive development. Malnourished children are therefore at high risk of illness and mortality [2].

Worldwide, nearly one billion people are undernourished and more than two billion are deficient in micronutrients. Approximately 115 million children less than 5 years suffer from underweight, 178 million suffer from stunting and 43 million are overweight. In developing countries, growth retardation affects about one child under 5 years on three, with 90% of all the cases in Africa and Asia [3]. At this age, the number of children suffering from underweight is estimated at 30 million in Africa and 71 million in Asia [4].

Nutritional anthropometry is the most practical means for the assessment of the nutritional status of preschool children as well as for the identification of the extent of malnutrition problems among a particular community. Anthropometric measurements include physical measurements like body weight and height of children and based on the weight and height, a number of indices have been suggested such as weight for age, height for age and weight for height. The US National Center of Health Statistics (NCHS) in 1975 has advocated expressing the deviation from anthropometric measurements of the reference median in terms of standard deviation or Z-scores [5]. Following the classification of WHO database on child growth and using Z-scores analysis; malnutrition problems among preschool children, have been categorized into three categories: Stunting, reflecting a long term growth faltering.

A stunted child is defined as one whose height for age Z-score (HAZ) is less than -2 SD of the reference median. Wasting, reflecting acute or recent growth disturbances. A wasted child is defined as one with weight for height Z-score (WHZ) less than -2SD below the reference median. Underweight, reflecting a combination of disturbances in linear growth and body proportion, underweight child is defined as one with weight for age Z-score (WAZ) less than -2 SD of the reference median.

In Cameroon, the latest nutrition survey conducted by the National Statistics Institute reported high rate and increasing prevalence of stunting (33%), underweight (15%) and wasting (6%) in children under 5 years. It also showed that the height and weight disorders are more common in rural than urban areas. Malnutrition is one of the most important health and welfare problems among infants and young children in Cameroon. It is a result of both inadequate food intake and illness. Inadequate food intake is a consequence of insufficient food available at the household level, improper feeding practices, or both. Improper feeding practices include both the quality and quantity of foods offered to young children as well as the timing of their introduction. Poor sanitation puts young children at increased risk of

illness, in particular diarrheal disease, which adversely affects their nutritional status. Both inadequate food intake and poor environmental sanitation reflect underlying social and economic conditions [6].

Malaria is an infectious, hematologic disease [7], caused by a protozoan parasite called Plasmodium species and the most dangerous is Plasmodium falciparum (*P. falciparum*) which occurs in Africa [8]. There are four other parasites which are not as dangerous as *P. falciparum*, these being *P. vivax*, *P. ovale*, *P. malariae*, and *P. knowlesi* [8]. Plasmodium falciparum is the most prevalent parasite in Africa especially in Sub-Saharan Africa and is estimated to be the cause of 99% of malaria in 2016, while outside Africa *P. vivax* is the most predominant vector [8]. In malaria endemic countries, many *P. falciparum* infections are asymptomatic, Cameroon inclusive. Plasmodium falciparum infections may result in severe, uncomplicated or asymptomatic malaria. Asymptomatic malaria is defined as the presence of malaria parasites in people and absence of malaria-related symptoms such as temperature > 37.5C [9]. Asymptomatic malaria occurs as a result of continuous exposure to malaria infections, leading to the acquisition of partial immunity against complications such as cerebral malaria and the accumulation of the "reservoir of infection" [9]. Aside from being it a reservoir for malaria transmission, asymptomatic carriage causes several other challenges including but not limited to anaemia, stunting, and cognitive impairment in school children.

It was therefore against this background that this study was aimed to identify then, measure factors that predisposed school aged children to malaria infection, as well as to assess their nutritional status, in Bamenda, North West region of Cameroon.

Extreme under-nutrition, known as starvation, chronic hunger, and severe acute malnutrition (SAM) or moderate acute malnutrition (MAM) may have symptoms that include: a short height, thin body, very poor energy levels, and swollen legs and abdomen. Those who are undernourished often get infections and are frequently cold. Malnutrition during the early stages of development can have negative and severe effects on growth and intellectual development. This effect on a child's intellectual quotient makes it harder for them later in life to achieve their true potential abilities. Prevalence of asymptomatic malaria infection among primary school children was reported as 14.3% in North Western Tanzania. This same study reported that school age children are the age group most commonly infected with malaria parasites and their infections are usually asymptomatic, go unnoticed and thus never get treated, resulting in anaemia, reduced ability to concentrate and learn in school, and if sick lead to school absenteeism. High level of poverty which

has a definite effect on nutritional status has been linked to the endemicity of malaria in the Sub-Saharan Africa [10]. Several studies have shown associations between malaria and protein energy malnutrition, poor growth and certain micronutrient deficiencies among children [11].

Despite sufficient quantity and diversity of food resources in Cameroon, especially in the North West Region, where many foods are produced, malnutrition rates among children under 5 years persist and are at rise [12]; and malaria is the main cause of morbidity and mortality, accounting for 40 – 50% of hospital consultations and 23% of hospitalisations [13]. It was therefore, due to the negative health impacts of under nutrition and malaria infection in school aged children that this study was conceived.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A cross-sectional study design look at a population at a single point in time, using a cross section of a group and variables are recorded for each participant. They are relevant when assessing the prevalence of disease, attitudes and knowledge among patients or health personnel. This allow researchers to compare many different variables at the time, it's cheap and quick but requires a larger sample size as well as allow bias to affect results when there is a non-response during data collection. A cross sectional study design was therefore used to assess and manage the nutritional status of school aged children affected by malaria in Bamenda.

Study Area

The study was carried out in two selected hospitals; Regional Hospital Bamenda and District Hospital Nkwen formally known as CMA Nkwen. The Regional Hospital Bamenda is a Referral hospital found in Mankon, precisely in Bamenda II, in Mezam Division of the North West Region of Cameroon. It is subdivided into departments which include: Hemodialysis, ophthalmology, intensive care unit, emergency unit, pharmacy, internal medicine, maternity (post and antenatal units), treatment centre, theatre, social services, radiology, surgery, nephrology, outpatient department, paediatric unit which is the area of study. The District Hospital Nkwen is located in mile 2 directly opposite Amour Mezam travelling agency in Bamenda, North West Region of Cameroon. It's headed by a Medical Doctor and has Assistant General Supervisor. It is subdivided into wards (female, male, paediatric), maternity, ANC, infant welfare clinic and family planning, theatre, laboratory and casualty.

Study Population and Study Procedure

The populations of this study included all children aged 2-10years attending nursery and primary schools in Bamenda. Children aged 2-10years who lived and attended schools in nursery and primary schools in Bamenda whose teachers and parents gave consent

were included in the study while children who were seriously ill and those whose parents did not give consent were excluded. Nutritional status was evaluated using anthropometric, dietary, and clinical assessment of school aged children affected by malaria.

Anthropometric Assessment

Children were weighed and measured as per the WHO guidelines on Anthropometry.

Measuring the Height and Weight

- Weight, a calibrated scale was used and checked daily against a known weight prior use.
- Before use the balance was placed on hard flat surface and setting to zero.
- Shoes and heavy clothes were removed and children weighed with minimum possible clothes.
- Weight was recorded to the nearest 0.1-0.5 Kg.
- Height was measured using a non-stretch tape fixed to the wall or stadiometer.
- After removing the shoes, each child was asked to stand on the floor; feet together and with heels, buttocks, and back of the shoulders touching the wall adjacent to the tape.
- The child was asked to look forward so that the line of vision was parallel to the floor with arms hanging on the sides.
- The height was measured to the nearest 0.1 cm.

Measuring the Mid Upper Arm Circumference

The MUAC of each child was measured using a tape made of three colours.

Red indicating severe acute malnutrition, Yellow indicating moderate acute malnutrition and, the Green indicating nutritional status [3].

- The parent, child, guardian or teacher was asked to remove any clothing on the child's arm with the child in a standing or sitting position.
- The tape was wrapped around the mid upper arm (left arm) of the child and readings noted.
- The measurement was read to the nearest 0.1cm and recorded on the questionnaire. (See MUAC classification in appendices).

Determination of Malaria Status

Rapid diagnostic tests were done to determine the children's malaria status. This was done using the P. falciparum Antigen rapid kit according to the manufacturer's instructions. The thumb was cleaned with swabs provided and pricked with the lancet to obtain capillary blood. The blood sample was collected using the loop and blotted into a small hole on the rapid test kit labeled the sample part A. Two drops of buffer were added to the buffer part B. The test result was read after 15minutes [14].

Clinical Assessment

The children under study were examined for signs of nutrient deficiency and assessment was focused on the

child's hair, skin, mouth, nails, eyes, extremities. Clinical signs of nutrient deficiency included: pallor (on the nails and conjunctiva), weakness and pitting oedema on legs and feet, extended abdomen, dryness in the eyes, dry skin, hair loss, and severe visible wasting [15]. To determine the presence of oedema, pressure was applied with the thumb on both feet and observed for pitting oedema.

Measurement of Body Temperature

The children's body temperature was measured with Omron digital thermometer. The thermometer was placed in the armpits of the children; the body temperature appeared on the screen after 5-10 seconds and was documented for every child. Fever was characterised as an axillary temperature >37.5C [14].

Dietary Assessment

To assess for dietary habits, a structured 24hr diet recall which was broken down into meals (breakfast, launch, super, snacks) was used to determine the foods and drinks consumed by the child during the past 24hours. The child, mother or guardian was asked the different foods and drinks the child had eaten during the past 24hrs. Food groups considered were cereals/roots, vegetables, fruits, legumes/lentils, meat/fish/eggs, and milk/dairy products. Each of the food items recorded was coded for nutrient analysis using the Food Composition Table.

Diagnostic Methods

Moderate acute malnutrition was defined as weight for height of ≥ -3 and < -2 z-score. Severe acute malnutrition was defined as weight for height z-score of < -3 . Stunting was defined as height for age z-score of < -2 .

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria: - children aged 2-10years, their caretakers/teachers/ parents who gave consent, lived and schooled in Bamenda

Exclusion criteria:-Children aged 2-10years, their caretakers/parents/teachers who were seriously ill, did not give consent, and were not available in Bamenda during the time of the survey were not included in the study.

Sampling Techniques

Systemic sampling and Random sampling technique was used to select children aged 2-10 years who lived and schooled in Bamenda.

Study Variable

Dependent variable: - Malnutrition was indicated by stunting, wasting, underweight and obesity.

Independent variable: -

- Child characteristics; age, gender, tribe, religion.
- Maternal characteristics; education level, occupation, income.

- Environmental health condition; water supply, sanitation and housing condition.

Sample Size

The sample size was determined by using the Taro Yamane Formula: $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$;

Where n = corrected sample size; N = population size; e = margin of error (MoE). The number of children aged 2-10years who lived and schooled in Bamenda equal to 50,000.

Margin of error=5%; $n=50,000 / (1+50,000(0.05^2))=50,000/126= 396.8$ which is approximately 397.

Therefore, per Taro Yamane formula a sample size of 397 was used.

Pre-Testing

The questionnaire was pretested among few selected children and their caretakers/ teachers/parents for accuracy and clarity of questionnaire after which any wrongly asked questions or unnecessary material was eliminated and the questionnaire adjusted to complete the study.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The researcher submitted her questionnaire to her supervisor for examination and correction. The questionnaire was pre-tested prior to data collection for validity among few selected children and their parents in Bamenda.

The questionnaires were checked on a daily basis to identify corrections, and to verify if it was completed or well understood by respondents.

Data Collection Techniques

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire which was developed and designed to suit all children aged 2-10 years who lived and schooled in Bamenda. The structured questionnaire was self-administered to respondents by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into parts to cover all the specific objectives of the study. It constituted both closed and open ended questions.

Data Analysis

The collected data was reviewed and entered into Excel sheets for analysis for computing for means, and standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was accomplished using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), version 20 for unpaired t-test. Data was used to calculate Z-scores of anthropometric measurements, height for age, and weight for height and weight for age as compared with the National Center of Health Statistics (NCHS/WHO) reference values. Z scores (standard deviation scores): The Z-score represents how far the data are distributed (higher or lower) around the reference median.

Following the classification of WHO database on child growth: Stunted child is defined as one whose height for age (HAZ) is less than -2 SD of the reference median, reflecting a long term growth faltering. Wasted child is

defined as one with weight for height (WHZ) less than - 2 SD below the reference median, which reflects acute or recent growth disturbances. Underweight child is defined as one with weight for age (WAZ) less than -2 SD of the reference median, reflecting a combination of disturbances in linear growth and body proportion.

Ethical Consideration

Authorization was obtained from the following hierarchies:

- College of Technology (The University of Bamenda).
- Regional Delegation of Public Health.
- Study site.
- Informed consent from participants.

Consent was documented and validated by signing. Issues surrounding confidentiality, privacy and the purpose of the study were explained.

Results and discussion

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics

From the results, the Socio-demographic data of the study showed that 16.9% of the respondents were aged

2-3years with frequency of 67/397; 24.4% of the respondents were aged 4-5years with frequency of 97/397; 19.4% of the respondents were aged 6-7years with frequency of 77/397; 26.4% of the respondents were aged 8-9years with frequency of 105/397 and 12.8% of the respondents were aged 10 years with frequency of 51/397.

Also, the results revealed that 47.6% of the respondents were males with frequency of 189/397 while 52.4% of the respondents were females with frequency of 208/397.

A total of 17.1% of the respondents were civil servants with frequency of 68/397; 29.2% of the respondents were Traders with frequency of 116/397, 12.8% of the respondents were Farmers with frequency of 51/397 and 40.8% of the respondents were of other occupations not specified with frequency of 162/397.

With regards to religion, 64% of the respondents were Christians with frequency of 254/397, 9.8% of the respondents were Muslims with frequency of 39/397 and 26.2% of the respondents were of other religions not specified with frequency of 104/397. This is illustrated in the table below.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics: Case of Age, Gender, Occupation, Religion

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	2-3years	67	16.9	16.9	16.9
	4-5years	97	24.4	24.4	41.3
	6-7years	77	19.4	19.4	60.7
	8-9years	105	26.4	26.4	87.2
	10 years	51	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Gender					
Gender	Male	189	47.6	47.6	47.6
	Female	208	52.4	52.4	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Occupation					
Occupation	Civil Servants	68	17.1	17.1	17.1
	Trader	116	29.2	29.2	46.3
	Farmer	51	12.8	12.8	59.2
	Others	162	40.8	40.8	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Religion					
Religion	Christian	254	64.0	64.0	64.0
	Muslim	39	9.8	9.8	73.8
	Others	104	26.2	26.2	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	

From the results, 9.3% of the respondents were Muslims with frequency of 37/397, 70.8% of the respondents were of Grassfield origin with frequency of 281/397 while 19.9% of the respondents were of a ethnicity not specified (79/397).

Results also revealed that, 65.2% of the respondents earned less than 50000 FRS with frequency of 259/397, 29.2% of the respondents earned up to 100000 FRS with frequency of 116/397, 5.3% of the respondents earned up to 200000 FRS and 3% of the respondents earned up to 300000 FRS.

As concern the level of education, 36.8% of the respondents had attained primary education with frequency of 146/397, 49.9% of the respondents had attained secondary education with frequency of

198/397 and 13.4% of the respondents had attained higher education with frequency of 53/397. This is illustrated in the table below.

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics: Case of Ethnicity

Ethnicity					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Ethnicity	Muslim	37	9.3	9.3	9.3
	Grass Field	281	70.8	70.8	80.1
	Others	79	19.9	19.9	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Monthly Income of Parents/Guardian					
Monthly income	<50,000frs	259	65.2	65.2	65.2
	51,000-100,000frs	116	29.2	29.2	94.5
	101,000-200,000frs	21	5.3	5.3	99.7
	201,000-300,000frs	1	.3	.3	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Level of education of Parents/Guardian					
Level of education	Primary education	146	36.8	36.8	36.8
	Secondary Education	198	49.9	49.9	86.6
	Higher Education	53	13.4	13.4	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	

Anthropometric Measurements

Mid Upper Arm Circumference and Classification

Results revealed that 67/397(16.8%) children within the age2-4years had a MUAC lessthan 11 cm, and were classified as severely malnourished. For children within the age 5-9 years, 53/397 (13.3%) had a MUAC lessthan13.5cm and were classified as severely malnourished while 7/397(1.7%) children who were aged 10 years had a MUAC lessthan16cm and were classified as severely malnourished.Furthermore, results showed that 52/397 (13%) children within the age 2-4years had a MUAC within 11-13cm, and were classified as moderately malnourished. Also, 116/397

(29.2%) children within the age 5-9years had a MUAC within13.5-14.5cm and were classified as moderately malnourished. While 40/397 (10%) children aged 10years had a MUAC within 16-18 cm, and were classified as moderately malnourished.

Lastly, a total of 45/397 (11.3%) children within the age2-4years had a MUAC greater than 13 cm, and were classified as normal. Also, results revealed that 14/397 (3.52%) children within the age 5-9years had a MUAC greater than 14.5cm and were classified as normal. While 3/397 (0.75%) of children aged 10years had a MUAC greaterthan18cm and were classified as normal.

This is illustrated in the table below.

Table 3: Mid Upper Arm Circumference of Respondents

MUAC CLASSIFICATION				
MUAC	Ages	Frequency	Percentages	Classification
2-4years 5-9years 10years	<11cm	67	16.8	SEVERE
	<13.5cm	53	13.3	
	<16 cm	7	1.7	
2-4years 5-9years 10years	11-13cm	52	13.0	MODERATE
	13.5- 14.5cm	116	29.2	
	16- 18 cm	40	10.0	
2-4years 5-9years 10 years	>13cm	45	11.3	NORMAL
	>14.5cm	14	3.52	
	> 18 cm	3	0.75	

Body Mass Index and Classification

The results revealed that for girls who were aged 2years, 3% were severely malnourished, 3.7% were moderately malnourished, 1.5%were normal, 0.5% were overweightwhile1.5% were obsessed.

Also, results showed that for girls, who were aged 3 years, 1.2% were severely malnourished, 4.5% were moderately malnourished, 0% were normal, 0.5% were overweight while 0.7%ofthegirls were obsessed.

To add, for girls who were aged 4 years, 1.7% were severely malnourished, 0.5% had moderate malnutrition, 1.2% were normal, 1.1% were overweight while 0% of the girls were obsessed.

Furthermore, for girls who were aged 5 years, 3.2% had severe malnutrition, 2.5% had moderate malnutrition, 0.7% were normal, 0.7% were overweight while 0.5% of the girls were obsessed.

From the results, 2.5% of girls aged 6years had severe malnutrition, and 3% of the girls had moderate malnutrition, 0.5% of the girls were normal, 0.5% were overweight while 0.7% of the girls were obsessed.

Results showed that for girls who were aged 7 years, 1.7% had severe malnutrition, 0.5% had moderate

malnutrition, 0% were normal, 2.1% of girls were overweight while 1.1% were obsessed.

Also, the results revealed that 2.1% of girls aged 8years had severe malnutrition, and 3.2% of the girls had moderate malnutrition, 1.1% of the girls were normal, 1.2% of girls were overweight while 0% of the girls were obsessed.

For girls who were aged 9 years, 0.5% were severely malnourished, 2.5% were moderately malnourished, 0.7% were normal, 1.1% were overweight while 1.1% were obsessed.

Results revealed that 1.7% of girls aged 10years had severe malnutrition, 1.1% of the girls had moderate malnutrition, 0% of the girls were normal, 0% were overweight and 0% of the girls were obsessed.

Overall, a total of 76/397 (19.1%) girls were classified as moderately malnourished, 71/397(17.8%) girls were classified as severely malnourished, about 21/397(5.2%) girls had normal BMI, 30/397 (7.1%) girls were classified as being overweight while 22/397 (5.5%) of the girls were classified as obsessed.

Table 4: Girls BMI for Age

Age	Severe Malnutrition -3SD		Moderate Malnutrition -2SD		Normal		Overweight 2SD		Obsessed 3SD	
	frequency	%	frequency	%	frequency	%	Frequency	%	frequency	%
2years	12	3	15	3.7	6	1.5	2	0.5	6	1.5
3years	5	1.2	8	4.5	0	0	2	0.5	3	0.7
4years	7	1.7	2	0.5	5	1.2	4	1.1	0	0
5years	13	3.2	10	2.5	3	0.7	3	0.7	2	0.5
6years	10	2.5	12	3	2	0.5	2	0.5	3	0.7
7years	7	1.7	2	0.5	0	0	8	2.1	4	1.1
8years	8	2.1	13	3.2	2	1.1	5	1.2	0	0
9years	2	0.5	10	2.5	3	0.7	4	1.1	4	1.1
10years	7	1.7	4	1.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	71	17.8	76	19.1	21	5.2	30	7.1	22	5.5

From the results, 0.5% of boys who were aged 2years had severe malnutrition, and 2.1% of the boys had moderate malnutrition, 1.5% of the boys were normal and 0.5% of boys were overweight while 0.7% of the boys were obsessed.

Also, 1.2% of boys aged 3 years had severe malnutrition, 1.2% of the boys had moderate malnutrition, 2.2% of the boys were normal, 0.5% of the boys were overweight while 0.7% of the boys were obsessed.

Results revealed that 2.2% of boys aged 4years had severe malnutrition, 2.1% of the boys had moderate malnutrition, 1.2% of the boys were normal 1.1% of the

boys were overweight while 0% of the boys were obsessed.

The results also showed that 0.7% of boys aged 5years had severe malnutrition, 1.1% of the boys had moderate malnutrition, 0.7% of the boys were normal, 0.7%of the boys were overweight while0.5% of the boys were obsessed.

To add, 0.5% of the boys who were aged 6years had severe malnutrition, 4.7%oftheboys presented with moderate malnutrition, 0.5% of the boys were normal, 0.5%of the boys were overweight while 0.7% of the boys were obsessed.

Furthermore, about 1.5% of the boys who were aged 7 years presented with severe malnutrition, 0.5% of the

boys had moderate malnutrition, 0.7% of the boys were normal, 0.5% of the boys were overweight while 1.1% of the boys were obsessed.

About 2.1% of the boys aged 8years were severely malnourished, 1.1% had moderate malnutrition, 1.1% were normal, 1.2% were overweight and 0.7% were obsessed.

Moreover, the results showed that for boys aged 9 years, 0.5% of the boys had severe malnutrition, 0.5% of the boys presented with moderate malnutrition, 0.7% of the boys were normal, 1.1% were overweight while 1.1% of the boys were obsessed.

Lastly, about 1.2%of the boys who were aged 10years presented with severe malnutrition, 0.7% of the boys had moderate malnutrition, 2.1% of the boys were normal, and 1.7% of the boys were overweight while 1.5% of the boys were obsessed.

Overall, a total of 46/397 (11.5%) boys were classified under the BMI category of moderately malnourished, about 42/397 (10.5%) boys were classified as severely malnourished, 38/397 (9.5%) of the boys were classified as having a normal BMI, 26/397 (6.5%) were classified as being overweight while only 25/397 (6.2%) were classified as obese.

Table 5: Boys BMI for Age

Age	Severe Malnutrition -3SD		Moderate Malnutrition -2SD		Normal		Overweight 2SD		Obsessed 3SD	
	frequency	%	frequency	%	frequency	%	Frequency	%	frequency	%
2 years	2	0.5	8	2.1	6	1.5	2	0.5	3	0.7
3 years	5	1.2	5	1.2	9	2.2	2	0.5	3	0.7
4 years	9	2.2	8	2.1	5	1.2	4	1.1	0	0
5 years	3	0.7	4	1.1	3	0.7	3	0.7	2	0.5
6 years	2	0.5	5	4.7	2	0.5	2	0.5	3	0.7
7 years	6	1.5	2	0.5	3	0.7	2	0.5	4	1.1
8 years	8	2.1	4	1.1	4	1.1	5	1.2	3	0.7
9 years	2	0.5	2	0.5	3	0.7	4	1.1	4	1.1
10years	5	1.2	8	2.1	3	0.7	2	0.5	3	0.7
Total	42	10.5	46	10.5	38	9.5	26	6.5	25	6.2

From the results, children whose BMI category was overweight (p- value >0.05) had no statistical significant association with malaria status while children with a BMI category of severe, moderate, normal and obsessed revealed a statistical association (p-value <0.05) with malaria status.

Also, for the MUAC classification, only children classified as severe had a significant association (p-value <0.05) with malaria status while children who were classified as moderate and normal showed no statistical association (p- values >0.05) with malaria status.

Table 6: Correlation Between Anthropometric Data and Malaria Status

Comparison of the relationship between anthropogenic Data and Malaria Status				
BMI category	Negative	Positive	P-values	Regression
Severe	0 (%)	104 (29.6%)	.000	.277
moderate	1 (2.1 %)	126 (35.8 %)	.000	1.000
Normal	42 (91.3%)	56 (15.9%)	.000	.246
overweight	2 (4.2%)	44 (12.5%)	.715	.267
obsessed	1 (2.1%)	21 (5.9%)	.000	-.312
total	46	351		
MUAC				
Severe	0 (%)	111 (31.6%)	.000	.277
moderate	7 (15.2%)	193(54.9 %)	.059	.782
Normal	39 (84.7%)	47 (13.3%)	.893	1.000
total	46	351		

Clinical parameters

The clinical data revealed that 299/397(75.3%) of the respondents had normal hair while only 98/397 (24.7%)

of the respondents had Brittle hair. The results also showed that 76/397(19.1%) of the respondents had Normal eyes while 162/397 (40.3%) of the respondents

had Pale yes, 159/3397 (40.1%) of the respondents had both pale and dry eyes Also, the results showed that 279/397 (70.3%) of the respondents had no mouths ore while 118/397(29.7% of the respondents had mouths ore.

To add, 163/397 (41.1%) of the respondents had normal skin texture while 234/397 (58.9%) of the respondents had scaly skin texture.

Furthermore, 267/397 (67.3%) of the respondents presented with a normal abdomen while 130/397 (32.7%) had experienced Diarrhoea.

About 196/397 (49.4%) of the respondents had normal extremities while 201/397 (50.6%) of the respondents had weak extremities.

A total of 75/397 (18.9%) of the respondents had normal nails while 322/397 (81.1%) had pallornails.

Lastly,193/397(48.6%) of the respondents presented with temperatures less than 37.5while 204/397 (51.4%) of the respondents presented with temperatures greaterthan 37.5.

From the table below, the p values (<0.05) showed that there was a significant association between the clinical parameters and malaria status.

Table 7: Clinical Parameters

Hair					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	Normal	299	75.3	75.3	75.3
	Brittle	98	24.7	24.7	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Eyes					
Valid	Normal	76	19.1	19.1	19.1
	Pale	162	40.8	40.8	59.9
	Pale, Dryness	159	40.1	40.1	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Mouth					
	Normal	279	70.3	70.3	70.3
	Mouth sore	118	29.7	29.7	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Skin texture					
Valid	Normal	163	41.1	41.1	41.1
	Scaly	234	58.9	58.9	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Abdomen					
Valid	Normal	267	67.3	67.3	67.3
	Diarrhea	130	32.7	32.7	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Extremities					
	Normal	196	49.4	49.4	49.4
	Weak	201	50.6	50.6	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Nails					
	Normal	75	18.9	18.9	18.9
	Pallor	322	81.1	81.1	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Temperature					
	<37.5	193	48.6	48.6	48.6
	>37.5	204	51.4	100.0	100.0
	Total	397	100.0	100.0	

Figure 1: Correlation Between Clinical Data and Malaria Status

Biochemical Data of Respondents

The tables below shows that 46/397 (11.6%) of the respondents were negative for malaria while 351/397

(88.4%) of the respondents were tested positive for malaria.

Table 8: Biochemical Data of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Negative	46	11.6	11.6	11.6
Positive	351	88.4	88.4	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	

Factors that predispose children to malaria

Table 9: Factors that Predispose Children to Malaria

Do you often eat food like carrots, fish, milk, eggs?				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	173	43.6	43.6	43.6
No	224	56.4	56.4	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Do you usually find difficulties with vision or feel dryness in your eyes?				
Yes	161	40.6	40.6	40.6
No	236	59.4	59.4	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Do you sleep under a mosquito net?				
Yes	156	39.3	39.3	39.3
No	241	60.7	60.7	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Is there stagnant water or bushes around your house?				

Yes	232	58.4	58.4	58.4
No	165	41.6	41.6	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Monthly income of parents/care givers?				
<50,000frs	261	65.7	65.7	65.7
51,000-100,000frs	113	28.5	28.5	94.2
101,000-200,000frs	22	5.5	5.5	99.7
201,000-300,000frs	1	.3	.3	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Do you often eat green leafy vegetables, apples, bananas, beans, meat, chicken?				
Yes	162	40.8	40.8	40.8
No	235	59.2	59.2	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	
Do you often eat okra, red meat and poultry, peanuts, beans, milk, pork, yogurt, pumpkin seeds, mushroom, guavas, pears?				
Yes	96	24.2	24.2	24.2
No	301	75.8	75.8	100.0
Total	397	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Correlation Between Factors that Predispose Children to Malaria and Malaria Status

The results, 173/397 (43.6%) of the respondents agreed that they often eat carrots/fish/milk/eggs while 224/397 (56.4%) of the respondents disagreed.

Also, 161/397 (40.6%) of the respondents accepted that they had difficulty in vision and felt dryness in the eyes while 236/397 (59.4%) of the respondents disagreed.

To add, results revealed that 156/397 (39.3%) of the respondents accepted that they sleep under a mosquito net while 241/397 (60.7%) of the respondents did not accept.

Furthermore, 232/397(58.4%) of the respondents accepted that they have stagnant water/bushes around the house while about 165/397 (41.6%) of the respondents refused. The results also showed that 261/397 (65.7%) of the respondents' parents/care givers earn less than 50 000 FRS, 113/397 (28.5%) of the respondents' parents/care givers earn up to 100 000 FRS, 22/397 (5.5%) of the respondents' parents/care givers earn up to 200 000frs while only 1/397(0.3%) of the respondents' parents/care givers earn up to 300 000frs.

The study results revealed that, 162/397 (40.8%) of the respondents accepted that they often eat green leafy vegetables, apples, bananas, beans, meat, and chicken while, 235/397 (59.2%) disagreed.

Lastly, about 96/397(24.2%) of the respondents accepted that they often eat okra, red meat and poultry, peanuts, beans, milk, pork, yogurt, pumpkin seeds, mushroom, guavas, pears while 301/397 (75.8%) of the respondents disagreed.

From the table below, the p values (<0.05) shows that there was a significant association between factors that predispose children to malaria and malaria status even though Respondents who had bushes or stagnant water around their house showed no significant association (p value >0.05).

Discussion

Malaria is a parasitic infection which greatly affects the nutritional status of children. Nutritional status is closely tied to the immune response to infections being on one hand an important determinant of the risk and prognosis of infectious diseases, and on the other hand being influenced by infection [14]. The lack of certain essential nutrients (vitamin A, Iron, zinc) which help the body to boost its immune system can make it susceptible to malaria infection [16]. In this study, the nutritional status of school aged children in Bamenda was assessed through anthropometric measurements, dietary data, and clinical evaluation.

Socio-demographic characteristics of Respondents

The study revealed that majority of the respondents was females. This could be due to differences in social, cultural and behavioural aspects which may influence one's risk of exposure to mosquito vectors, perception

of illness and health seeking behaviour [17]. Majority of the respondents were aged between 8 and 9years. A study reported that in malaria-endemic areas, the manifestation of malaria cases is a function of immunity with respect to age and exposure to the parasite; reasons why asymptomatic malaria is common among older children [18]. Most of the respondents were Christians of the grass field origin, whose parents had occupations not specified with a monthly income of less than 50,000 FRS and had attained secondary education. This could be as a result of the on-going socio-political crisis in this locality.

Anthropometric Measurements of Respondents

According to the Body Mass Index classification for girls, a total of 76/397 (19.1%) of the respondents were moderately malnourished, 71/397(17.8%) were severely malnourished, 30/397(7.1%) were overweight, 21/397(5.2%) were normal, 22/397(5.5%) were obese. while for boys, 46/397(11.5%) of the respondents were moderately malnourished, 41/397(10.5%) were severely malnourished, 38/397(9.5%) were normal, 26/397(6.5%) were overweight and 26/397(6.2%) were obese. A study reported that infections associated with diarrhoea such as malaria causes protein loss, improper nutrient absorption, low ascorbic acid concentration, decreased serum iron and zinc [19] thus resulting in a low BMI. For the mid upper arm circumference, majority (29.2%) were moderately malnourished. This could be linked to the respondents' parents monthly incomes which was less than 50,000frs as they could not afford enough food for the household.

Clinical data of Respondents

Findings on the clinical data of respondents revealed that majority (81.1%) had pallor nails. This is not surprising because according to Matiello et al., in 2020, they reported that some of the clinical manifestations of iron deficiency include unexplained fatigue, weakness, pallor, irritability and hair loss. More than half of the respondents (58.9%) presented with scaly skin. This tie with the study of Al-Refu & Tarawneh in 2013 who reported features of zinc deficiency to include photosensitivity, hair loss, persistent cutaneous infections and dry skin [20]. Also, majority (50.6%) of the respondents had weak extremities. This goes back to explain the work of Matiello et al., in 2020 where they reported some of the features of iron deficiency to include fatigue and weakness [21]. Statistics showed that, (40 .8%) of the respondents had pale eyes and (40.1%) had pale and dry eyes. This statistics are in line with the study of Matiello et al., in 2020 [21] that reported pallor as one of the clinical signs of iron deficiency and also support the work of Tadesse et al. (2005) who reported that clinical features of vitamin A deficiency include dryness in the eye [22].

Dietary Data of Respondents

The study revealed that majority (70.5%) of the respondents consumed mostly cereals/ roots followed by legumes (12.6%), meat/fish/eggs (5.5%), milk/dairy products (4.5%), and lastly vegetables (3.8%), fruits (3%). A cross sectional survey in an urban area in South Africa where more than 80% of the infants usually consumed cereals such as porridge, showed that many of these infants were anaemic, deficient in Vitamin A or Zinc [19]. These are nutrients that could help boost the immune system against malaria infection. Studies have also shown that the consumption of fruits in sub Saharan Africa is significantly lower than that of vegetables with only urban populations consuming the recommended minimum [19].

This study revealed that there was a significant association (P value < 0.05) between the foods consumed and malaria status in school aged children in Bamenda.

Factors that predispose children to malaria

Statistics showed that majority (56.4%) of the respondents did not often eat foods like carrots, fish, milk, and eggs. These are foods which are high in vitamin A and vitamin A is one of the micronutrient essential for the immune system to fight against the malaria parasite. A study reported that preformed vitamin A is found in foods such as butter, egg yolk, cod liver oil [24]; another study reported that foods containing beta carotenes include; red and orange vegetables, carrots [25].

Also, Majority (60.7 %) of the respondents did not sleep under a mosquito net. This finding support a study which revealed that lower income, house type, distance to health centers, awareness of malaria and use of mosquito nets were correlated with the occurrence of malaria [26].

Furthermore, majority (58.4%) of the respondents accepted that there is stagnant water or bushes around their house. This finding is true with those of a study which reported that rural areas are associated with open fields, stagnant water, and green vegetation which provides breeding grounds for mosquitoes especially during the rainy season [26]; and this study was carried out in the rainy season, reason why the malaria infection was more prevalent in a rural area like Bamenda.

To add, findings revealed that majority (65.7%) of the respondents' parents monthly income was less than 50,000 FRs. This is in line with the results from a study which reported that lower income, house type, distance to health centres were correlated with the occurrence of malaria [26]. This researcher further reported an association between poverty, poor living conditions and malaria and the results showed that children from rich families were less likely to suffer from malaria.

More so, statistics showed that majority (59.2%) of the respondents did not often eat green leafy vegetables, apples, beans, bananas, meat, chicken. A study reported that food containing heme iron include; meat, seafood, poultry which are easily absorbable and contributes to about 10% or more of our total absorbed iron while non-heme iron is derived from plants and iron- fortified foods, and is less absorbed [27].

Lastly, more than half (75.8%) of the respondents did not often eat okra, red meat, poultry, pear, guava, beans, milk, pumpkin seeds, pork, yoghurt, mushroom, peanuts. This results ties with the findings of Rangan & Sammam (2012), who reported that Zinc is widely distributed in the Australian food supply and based on the 1995 data, meats, fish, poultry, dairy foods contributes to the diets of Australian children [28].

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to assess the nutritional status of school aged children affected by malaria in Bamenda.

Findings revealed that, majority of the respondents were moderately malnourished according to the BMI and MUAC classification.

The rate of consumption of cereals/roots by the respondents was extremely high as compared to vegetables, fruits, legumes, meat/fish/eggs, milk/dairy products.

Many respondents presented with pallor nails, pale and dry eyes followed by weak extremities and scaly skin texture.

The factors that predisposed children to malaria were that majority (60.7%) did not sleep under mosquito net, 58.4% accepted there is stagnant water and bushes around their house, 65.7% had monthly incomes <50,000frs, 59.2% did not eat green leafy vegetables, bananas, apples, meat, beans, chicken, 75.8% did not eat okro, meat, poultry, guavas, mushroom, pumk in seeds, pork, beans, yoghurt.

This study concluded that moderate malnutrition and little consumption of vegetables, legumes, fruits, meat/fish/egg, milk/dairy products were nutritional problems on the nutritional status of school aged children affected by malaria in Bamenda.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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